

Stress Redistribution around Notches in CVI C-SiC Composites

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SUMMARY

The effect of nonlinear stress-strain behavior due to matrix cracking on stress redistribution around notches in CVI C/SiC composites laminate is analyzed. A constitutive model is developed and used to predict strain development around notches. The results indicate that both shear damage band and the tensile inelastic deformation contribute to the notch insensitivity of CVI C/SiC composite. The shear damage band plays a key role. It can reduce the geometrical discontinuity of the notches, and the tensile strain concentration at the notch tip is reduced to nearly to their net section magnitudes. The tensile inelastic deformations of CVI C/SiC composites can cause the tensile stress concentrations to be lower than the tensile strain concentrations.

Keywords: Composite, Ceramic, damage, notches, stress redistribution